

Stay with Reincarnate this 2024!

1 message

Reincarnate EU project <reincarnate@australo.org>

31 January 2024 at 12:01

Reply-To: reincarnate@australo.org

To: reincarnate@australo.org

REINCARNATE

Funded by
the European Union

Dear **changemaker**,

In our fourth issue, we tell you the **project's latest advances**. Having surpassed the eighteen months of implementation and having the official review meeting knocking on the door, you will learn about the project achievements and better understand our mission and vision.

We invite you to follow us on our channels to stay updated on all the project's activities.

Enjoy your reading!

Reincarnate Talks

how are we reshaping the built environment?

#ReincarnaTalks

The [#ReincarnaTalks](#) video series showcase the people working behind our innovations, demonstrators and research. They explain contributions and opinions to pave the way for landing and establishing a Reincarnation Practice - circularity in the built environment.

[Get to know more!](#)

REINCARNATE HAS JOINED THE TECH4UCONSTRUCTION CLUSTER

The Reincarnate project has joined the [Tech4EUConstruction cluster](#) to revolutionise the construction sector collaboratively with co-founder projects **Beeyonders**, **Robetarme**, **HumanTech** and other members such as **Reconmatic**, **BIM2TWIN** and **Incube**. The cluster aims to develop and demonstrate new technologies to further digitalise and automatise the European construction sector, targeting to increase its safety and attractiveness for workers.

[Learn more about the cluster!](#)

SCIENCE AND RESEARCH BEHIND REINCARNATE'S INNOVATIONS

Reinventing data driven materials design

Scientific publication on data-driven design

Software for the inverse design of sustainable

In the frame of a hackathon, [our publication](#) demonstrates how LLMs can impact chemistry, materials science and beyond. We are eager to continue exploring this synergy of AI and human intuition in materials science.

[Discover more!](#)

This [publication](#) presents a novel approach for developing sustainable building materials through ecologically informed Sequential Learning (SL), proving that by adopting a data-driven approach, sustainable building materials can be developed much quicker than commonly anticipated.

[Explore the paper!](#)

cementitious materials

The [article](#) is significant in creating adaptable and reusable solutions, especially in our work with high-performance materials made from recycled materials. Using data-driven methods can be a helpful way to produce sustainable materials such as cementitious.

[Check it out!](#)

REINCARNATE AROUND EUROPE

Over the past few months, we actively participated in diverse events and conducted workshops to spotlight our project while fostering meaningful discussions with our stakeholders. In Poland, our PLGBC colleagues took part in the [13th edition of the Polish Real Estate Forum](#), a relevant gathering within the real estate industry. Moreover, our partner TUDelft showcased their expertise at the ["29th edition of the ERES annual conference" in London](#), presenting the paper titled "A comprehensive literature review on the decision criteria for adaptive reuse throughout the AR process," delving into real estate matters at a scholarly level.

Continuing our endeavours in Poland, our engagement extended to the hybrid and international sustainable building event hosted by our partner, the ["PLGBC Green Building Summit."](#) CEMEX Poland, another valued partner, participated in this event. Furthermore, the innovative spirit of our partners was highlighted when PLGBC presented our project, Reincarnate, at the ["Horizon 4 Poland 23"](#) event, emphasising its relevance to both the business and scientific sectors. Shifting our focus to Germany, our colleagues from BAM attended the [DIGICON 2023 convention in Munich](#), where they presented SLAMD, their open-source app for Reincarnate. The app received acclaim from renowned experts in digitalisation and influential decision-makers spanning industry, politics, and research.

Our team organised two physical workshops, one in [Rotterdam](#) discussing innovations in adaptive reuse-recycling and social-market initiatives and the other in [Sweden](#) delving into digital innovations related to sustainable adaptive reuse and recycling practices. These workshops provided platforms for insightful discussions and collaborative exploration of our green innovations.

INDUSTRY NEWS

Moving toward close-loop materials in the construction sector with new recycled aggregates

The construction industry is shifting towards using closed-loop materials. Before, they could be considered waste, but **thanks to partner CEMEX Polska, recycled aggregates have been added to product ranges.** These recycled aggregates are reprocessed materials, such as concrete, previously used in construction. As a result, the social, environmental and economic benefits are enormous for all the stakeholders.

[Find out more!](#)

How is Reincarnate aligned with the Global Agenda?

The latest United Nations [report](#) underscores a pressing need for decisive action and commitment to set the world on a sustainable trajectory. We're facing a universal stall in progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals. Significant strides were made **last year at COP28, as highlighted by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation. For the first time, the circular economy was a key part of the negotiated outcomes.** This milestone fuels our drive at Reincarnate as we work towards integrating into our mission. Our efforts are aligned with the Global Agenda and are specifically focused on contributing to achieving goals 9, 12 and 17. Goal 9 aims to foster innovation and infrastructure in industry, while goal 12 aims to encourage responsible consumption and production. Lastly, goal 17

emphasises the importance of partnerships to achieve sustainable development.

Check them out!

GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN SWEDEN

We gathered in Sweden from 19 to 20 October to discuss our progress, exchange ideas and plan their next steps before the review with the European Commission. Partner [Ragn-sells group](#) hosted the meeting and invited all 16 members to celebrate the General Assembly and visit their waste management treatment plant. This was a great opportunity for the team to learn and gain insights from the host partner.

[Read the full article!](#)

WELCOMING OUR ADVISORY BOARD

Advisory Board Meeting #1

In January, we first met with our **Advisory Board members**, the group of experts that will enhance our project. These seven members come from various fields, including science, engineering, economy, business and innovation. We are grateful for their support in helping us transform the construction industry into a circular one. In the virtual meeting, they started contributing their suggestions and questions.

Get to know them!

UPCOMING OPPORTUNITIES

“A Circular Built Environment in the Digital Age”

We invite you to read this **open-access book**. The publication connects and describes the many digital innovations that can drive circularity in the built environment. It is a joint effort of state-of-the-art experts in each field of digitalisation that is applied to circular construction. Moreover, it provides real-world examples of applications in the construction sector for each digital technology. Covering data, design, fabrication, and business as governance articles with a concluding perspective.

Read it!

The ASHVIN project hosts a webinar on open data and infrastructure maintenance

Register now!

For three years, **this European project** has worked on creating a digital twin technology solution boosting the productivity and safety of construction projects and infrastructure asset management. **Next Thursday, 22nd of February, from 12:00 to 13:00 CET, they will host the online interactive session “How does access to open data transform infrastructure maintenance? - Discussions and insights from research findings.”** The session aims to present insights into their work and results on open data framework and the social and technical developments for safer maintenance planning. The webinar will encourage participants to share their experiences and questions during the discussions. Let's learn the data-sharing practices of tomorrow!

RECONMATIC Clustering Event: Promoting Circularity in Construction

The RECONMATIC partners are delighted to invite you to the **online clustering event on circularity in construction**, hosted on the BUILD UP platform, on **28 February 2024 (13:00-14:30 CET)**. In this clustering event, sustainability experts and key stakeholders in construction, IT, automation, business and communication disciplines will be brought together to provide an overview of the European priorities for the **Twin Transition** in the sector and identify collaboration opportunities between five research initiatives with similar goals.

 Reconmatic Clustering Event

Promoting Circularity in Construction

28 February, 2024
13:00 - 14:30 CET, online

 Funded by the European Union

 UK Research and Innovation

 BUILD UP
The European portal for energy efficiency and renewable energy in buildings

[Learn more!](#)

Follow us and stay tuned!

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